

Copolymers. IV. Reactivity Ratios in *N*-Acryloylaminobenzoic Acids and Styrene Copolymers

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In continuation of our earlier studies on the synthesis and characterisation of copolymers¹, we report here the reactivity ratios of copolymerization of isomeric *N*-acryloylaminobenzoic acids with styrene. The reactivity ratios were calculated by the Kelen-Tudos method considering statistical average evaluation. From the values based on the Kelen-Tudos method, the Alfrey-Price *Q-e* values have been calculated for these monomers.

Copolymerizations of OAB, MAB and PAB respectively (M_1) with styrene (M_2) were carried out with feed ratios $M_1 : M_2 : : 10 : 90$ to $80 : 20$. An average of at least two analyses was used for each copolymer and the reproducibility of the results was found to be within $\pm 1.2\%$. The nitrogen content of OAB, MAB and PAB respectively in the copolymer was calculated from the 100% nitrogen content (7.33) in homopolymers of OAB, MAB and PAB respectively. The weight % conversion, composition of the various copolymers and nitrogen contents were determined.

Monomer reactivity ratios: Reactivity ratios for the systems styrene/OAB, MAB and PAB respectively, were calculated by using the Kelen-Tudos procedures^{2,8} considering statistical error evaluation. The reactivity ratios for the copolymerization of OAB (M_1) with styrene (M_2) are $r_1=0.937$, $r_2=0.262$, with MAB (M_1), they are $r_1=0.875$, $r_2=0.273$, and with PAB (M_1), they are $r_1=1.060$, $r_2=0.233$ respectively. The results indicate that at equal monomer concentrations, the adduct radical of styrene monomer is more likely to

systems in Table 1⁴. The reactivity ratios for OAB, MAB and PAB are appreciably greater than those of other acrylamide monomers in the system.

The Alfrey-Price *Q-e* values: The semiquantitative *Q-e* scheme is well known method of classifying the general reactivity of a given monomer. It is used in much the same way as the Hammett $\sigma\rho$ equation is used in organic chemistry to predict rates and equilibria⁵. Each monomer is characterised by resonance stability factor (*Q*) and polarity characteristic (*e*). *Q-e* scheme can be used to predict the reactivity ratios for a copolymerization reaction. It should be noted, however, that the validity and the limitations of the *Q-e* scheme are many and these limitations are well documented⁶. Despite these limitations, *Q* and *e* values for OAB, MAB and PAB monomers were determined (Table 2). The *Q-e* values allow to generalise for OAB, MAB and PAB monomers: they are polar molecules with an electron-deficient double bonds due to the polarisation effect of COOH group. The *Q*-values indicate a high resonance stability of the adduct radical similar to the general tendency observed for other monomers⁶.

TABLE 2—THE ALFREY-PRICE (*Q-e*) VALUES OF MONOMERS

Monomer	Kelen-Tudos method	
	<i>Q</i>	<i>e</i>
OAB	0.87	3.12
MAB	0.88	2.84
PAB	0.82	3.76
Styrene	0.99	-0.80

TABLE 1—COMPARABLE REACTIVITY RATIOS OF OTHER ACRYLAMIDE/STYRENE SYSTEMS

Monomer	$r_{\text{acrylamide}}$	r_{styrene}
Acrylamide	0.20	1.05
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl acrylamide	0.23	1.23
<i>N</i> -Octyl acrylamide	0.20	2.72
<i>N</i> -Octadecyl acrylamide	0.20	1.41
<i>N</i> -Isopropylidene bisacrylamide	0.56	1.57
OAB	0.93	0.26
MAB	0.87	0.27
PAB	1.06	0.23

react with other monomer relative to its own monomer. This would indicate a random copolymer with a strong tendency towards copolymerization. These reactivity ratios may be compared to reactivity ratios calculated for other acrylamide/styrene

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. The monomers *o*-, *m*- and *p*-*N*-acryloylaminobenzoic acids (M_1) were prepared as reported elsewhere⁷.

The required amounts of M_1 , M_2 (styrene), benzoyl peroxide (1.8% wt.) and 1,4-dioxane were placed in a glass tube, degassed and sealed. The copolymerizations were carried out in a thermostated oil-bath ($80 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and allowed to proceed to about 10–15% conversion. After 70 min, the contents were poured into a large amount of petroleum ether and washed several times with methanol for complete removal of unreacted monomers. The purified pale yellow powder copolymers